

More on the black-palp wolf spider *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 in South Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae)

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Abstract: The black-palp wolf spider *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 has a wide distribution in Southern Africa and is known from Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. The species is commonly found in agroecosystems and is recognised as one of five agrobiont species in South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pardosa* C.L. Koch, 1847 is represented by 528 species and subspecies, with 10 species recorded from South Africa. In this paper we provide more information on *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 a Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Montagu in the Western Cape. The species occurs wide throughout Southern Africa but is suspected to have a wider distribution in Africa. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces.

The aim of this paper is to collate all information on the species. This includes behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa, with notes on their agrobiont status. The data were gathered during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Pardosa crassipalpis Purcell, 1903

Pardosa crassipalpis Purcell, 1903: 138; Roewer, 1959: 122; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1977: 26; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 19.

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (4–5 mm). Carapace with dark lateral bands, the median yellow band broad, dilated in eye region; submarginal yellowish bands with a row of black spots laterally, the margin itself marked with a series of black bands (Figs 1, 3, 4). Anterior row of eyes straight or slightly procurved, the posterior median eyes are slightly larger than the laterals (Fig. 9). Sternum pale yellowish. Abdomen dark at the sides above (Figs 3–4), the median band more or less fused to form a single broad yellow area extending to spinnerets; with lateral bands decorated with black spots (in alcohol), white in live.

Legs pale yellowish, spotted, and banded with black, except tarsi; inferior spines on tibia, and metatarsus of first leg long. Epigyne longer than wide, somewhat triangular, with wavy margins and narrowed anteriorly (Figs 5–7).

Male (4–4.5 mm). Resembling the female in colour, except the distal segments of the legs are not banded and the first femur is more thickened at base in front. Palp distinct large covered with black setae (Figs 2 & 10).

LIFESTYLE

Pardosa crassipalpis is one of the smaller lycosids and, like the others, is a very quick-moving and agile ground spider. They can tolerate a wide range of habitats or ecological conditions (eurotopic), and they are found in all the floral biomes except the more arid ones (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They are present throughout the year and have a wide distribution throughout South Africa (Fig. 11).

The life cycle and some ecological aspects of the spider *P. crassipalpis* were studied (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1977). It is a univoltine species and the males pass through seven instars before reaching maturity and the females through eight. The egg sac is carried by the female (Figs 1 & 9) and during the reproductive phase the female spider produces an average of three egg sacs, with an average number of 23.3 eggs per sac. The construction of the egg sac took place at night and the new egg sac is bluish grey and later turns yellowish white. The complete egg sac is lenticular and is attached to the spinnerets of the female.

Figures 1–2. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 1. Female with egg sac. 2. Male showing the thick black palps, hence the common name. Photo credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Vida vd Walt.

Figures 3–7. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 3–4 Female dorsal view. 5–7. Epigynum. Photo credits: 3 & 5. Charles Haddad. 4 & 7. From Roewer (1959).

Twenty-three species of lycosids have been sampled in crops in South Africa but *P. crassipalpis* was the most abundant and sampled from crops such as cabbage, cotton, lucerne, maize, potatoes, sorghum, strawberries, sugar cane, sunflower, and tomatoes. They were also abundant in commercial pine plantations, and in apple, citrus, pistachio, pear, and pecans orchards. Therefore, the species is recognised as one of the agrobiont species in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

In surveys in strawberry fields at the ARC Roodeplaat campus, *P. crassipalpis* was the dominant species present, representing 82% of all the lycosids sampled and 63% of all the spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976, 1979). They were observed on the leaves and flowers of plants or running on the ground and hiding under the plants.

In cotton they were also the numerically dominant species and was recorded from five cotton-growing areas. They prey on red spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.) and various stages of cotton bollworm larvae (*Helicoverpa armigera*) in the laboratory (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). They are also the dominant family at the ground level in Bt cotton fields, representing 62.5% of all the spiders collected (Mellet *et al.*, 2006).

In pistachio orchards in the Northern Cape the 262 *P. crassipalpis* collected contributed 15.5% of all the spiders sampled. In Fig. 8 the number and phenology of *P. crassipalpis* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, are shown. They were present throughout the year, with adults peaking in October to January.

Figure 8. Numbers and phenology of *Pardosa crassipalpis* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, from August 2001 to July 2002 (pooled data of three orchards). Grey bars indicate immatures, white bars males, and black bars females. (from Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006).

Figures 9–10. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 9. Female with egg sac. 10. Male. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Coates (1974), Dippenaar-Schoeman (1976), and Botha (1986) found *P. crassipalpis* to be active predators of red spider mites (*Tetranychus cinnabarinus*) in various crops in South Africa. In the USA, Whitcomb *et al.* (1963) found that lycosids swarm over cotton plants at night in summer and that *Pardosa* spp. prey on pink bollworm moths. They presumably destroy first and second-instar larvae of the bollworm on the plant, as well as those that fall to the ground. Bollworm moths are also vulnerable to predation during their brief exposure on the soil surface following emergence from their pupae (Whitcomb, 1967).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Namibia, Botswana, South Africa, and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The known distribution of *P. crassipalpis* is shown in Fig. 11. Purcell (1903) described *P. crassipalpis* from specimens collected at the Hot Baths near Montagu. It is presently reported from all nine provinces. For detail locality records, see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021).

Figure 11. Known distribution of *Pardosa crassipalpis* in South Africa.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from six protected areas in South Africa. There are no known threats to the species and it is listed as Least Concern.

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